

Insights into Fish Growth Dynamics in Eyin-Osun River Ecosystem

¹*Asiru RA, ²Oladunjoye RY, ³Adedeji HA, ¹Olalekan, OB, ⁴Odusolu AA, ¹Oyedemi KA, ²Adeyemo DE, ¹Salami MA.

^{*1}Department of Biological Sciences, Federal University, Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria

²Department of Zoology and Environmental Biology, Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ago-Iwoye, Nigeria

³Department of Fisheries, Moddibo-Adama University of Technology, Yola, Nigeria

⁴Department of Aquaculture and Fisheries Management, University of Ibadan, Nigeria

*Correspondence: asiruraheemadkunle@gmail.com

Submission: 17th December, 2023; Accepted 8th January, 2024; Published: 28th February, 2024

Abstract

Fish growth dynamics are influenced by various factors such as species, environmental conditions, and available food resources. This study investigates the length-weight relationship, growth rate, and condition factors of fish species in Eyin-Osun River, Ogun State, Nigeria. Fishes were collected with the assistance of fisher folks and were immediately taken to laboratory in ice-chest cooler. Some morphometric measurements were taken to determine their growth dynamics. Four fish species (*Chrysichthys nigrodigitatus*, *Chrysichthys filamentous*, *Pelmatolpia mariae*, and *Sarotherodon melanotheron*) were observed during the study. All the four species exhibit negative allometric growth with no significant length-weight relationship (0.11, 0.91, 0.56 and 0.95 in *C. filamentous*, *C. nigrodigitatus*, *P. Mariae* and *S. melanotheron* respectively) in each of the four fish species ($b = 0.81 > 0.5 > 0.09 > 0.08$ in *C. filamentous*, *C. nigrodigitatus*, *P. Mariae* and *S. melanotheron* respectively). Condition factor was higher in *S. melanotheron* $>$ *P. Mariae* $>$ *C. filamentous* $>$ *C. nigrodigitatus* (2.46 ± 0.06^a , 2.13 ± 0.18^a , 1.09 ± 0.06^b , and 1.00 ± 0.06^b respectively).

Keywords: Length-weight, Condition factors, Growth, *Sarotherodon*, *Chrysichthys*, *Pelmatolpia*.

1.0 Introduction

Fish is any aquatic vertebrate animal that is covered with or without scales and equipped with two sets of paired fins and several unpaired fins [1]. They are found in diverse habitats, particularly, fresh and salt waters, estuaries and wetlands throughout the world. Their health and growth are directly related to water quality in which they live or are raised [2]. Fish growth is affected by physical, biological and chemical factors in water. [3] stated that environmental factors such as water quality, depth, season, and temperature could significantly impact the health and survival of fish. Fish growth dynamics has been used to monitor the wellbeing of fish over time.

To estimate the growth rates, length, age structures and other components in fish population dynamics, length and weight data are

required. Length-weight relationship (LWR) is used in assessment of fish condition in relation to their environment. They are important in fish stock assessment, proper exploitation and management [20]. The relationship of length-weight estimates condition factor of the fish species and fish biomass through the length frequency [4]. Condition factor (CF), a subject of LWR is used to determine the well-being of fishes [5]. LWR provides information on stock condition of fish [6], which is an important tool in fish biology, ecology, physiology, fisheries assessments, fish conservation, and fish management [7]. The objective of the current study was to provide insight into the growth dynamics of some fish species of Eyin-Osun river of Ogun State, Southwestern Nigeria. This report presents baseline information on the LWR and CF of fish of the Eyin-Osun river.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Description of Study Area

The study was carried out in Eyin-Osun; an area on the outskirts of Ijebu-Igbo town, head quarter of Ijebu-North Local Government of Ogun State (Long. 6°52'15.52"N - 6°52'15.56 and Lat. 4°5'59.41"E - 4°5'59.36"E)., The river is part of a river course of river Osun which flows southwards through the western states in Nigeria into the Lagos lagoon and the Atlantic Gulf of Guinea. It is called different names at different location along the course. The town's primary economic activities are timber, cocoa, exploration of mineral resources and it is home to many saw mills and also a developed quarry.

2.2 Sampling Procedure

Freshly caught fish samples from local fishermen, who had caught the fish in the early morning of the sampling day at the local landing site. The samples were washed, stored in ice chest, and transported to the laboratory for data taking. They were sorted, counted, identified and measured using standard keys [8], on getting into the laboratory. Total length and weight were measured to the nearest 0.1cm and 0.1g respectively using digital weighing balance and calibrated fish measuring board. Samples were collected fortnightly for three months between the months of February to June, 2022.

3.0 Results

Table 1: Morphometric parameters of fish species in Eyin Osun River water, Southwest, Nigeria

Parameters	<i>C. filamentous</i>	<i>C. nigrodigitatus</i>	<i>P. mariae</i>	<i>S. melanotheron</i>
Total Length (cm)	27.10±1.50 ^a	25.50±0.50 ^a	16.73±0.66 ^b	15.35±0.35 ^b
Standard Length(cm)	15.15±4.65 ^b	18.50±0.40 ^a	13.57±0.55 ^c	12.50±0.60 ^c
Weight(g)	198.50±20.50 ^a	180.00±1.00 ^a	98.67±5.36 ^b	89.00±4.00 ^b
Half Length(cm)	4.80±0.20 ^a	5.00±0.20 ^a	3.97±0.24 ^b	3.50±0.10 ^b
Fin Length(cm)	8.30±1.20 ^a	7.50±0.30 ^a	3.37±0.20 ^b	3.30±0.00 ^b
Caudal Fin Length(cm)	9.35±0.85 ^a	8.00±0.40 ^a	4.73±0.38 ^b	4.30±0.20 ^b
Caudal Peduncle Length(cm)	2.50±0.00 ^a	1.80±0.10 ^b	1.27±0.28 ^b	1.35±0.15 ^b
Caudal Peduncle diameter(cm)	2.75±0.15 ^b	3.60±0.30 ^a	2.40±0.17 ^b	2.05±0.15 ^b
Body Depth(cm)	7.55±0.35 ^a	7.20±0.20 ^a	7.10±0.12 ^a	7.40±0.20 ^a
Caudal Fin Tail	Forked	forked	Truncated	Truncated
Mouth Type	Sub-terminal	Sub-terminal	Terminal	Terminal
Sex	Female	Female	Female	Female

^{abc}Means (±Standard error of mean) in the same row having similar superscript are not significantly different at p < 0.05

Table 2: Length-Weight relationship of fish species in Eyin Osun River water, Nigeria

2.3 Data Analysis

Fish Length-weight relationship (LWR) was calculated using the formula $W = a + bL$ or aL^b [9].

Where W is body weight (g),

L is length of the body in (cm),

“a” is regression constant (Intercept) and;

“b” is regression coefficient (Slope).

The equation was then transformed into linear regression equation as:

$$\text{Log } W = \text{Log } a + b \text{ Log } L$$

Degree of association between weight and length variables was calculated by determination variables (R). The correlation (r^2) is the degree of association between the length and weight was computed from the linear regression analysis.

Condition factor

Condition factor is represented by K and was determined using the expression of Ricker,

$$K = \frac{100 W}{L^3}$$

All analyses were carried out using Microsoft excel statistical package on window 10 system.

Fish Species	TL (cm)	Weight (g)	a	b	r	r ²	P-value
<i>C. filamentous</i>	27.10±1.50 ^a	198.50±20.50 ^a	10.815	0.81	0.984	0.969	0.11
<i>C. nigrodigitatus</i>	25.50±0.50 ^a	180.00±1.00 ^a	12.048	0.50	0.998	0.996	0.91
<i>P. mariae</i>	16.73±0.66 ^b	98.67±5.36 ^b	9.114	0.08	0.631	0.398	0.56
<i>S. melanotheron</i>	15.35±0.35 ^b	89.00±4.00 ^b	7.563	0.09	0.999	0.998	0.95

^{abc} Means (±Standard error of mean) in the same column having similar superscript are not significantly different at $p < 0.05$; R^2 = Coefficient of determination; r = Correlation co-efficient; a = Rate of change of weight with length (intercept); b = weight at unit length (slope); TL = Total Length

Table 3: Growth and condition factor of fish species in Eyin Osun River water, Nigeria

Fish Species	Condition factor (K)	factor b	Growth type	Exponential Equation
<i>C. filamentous</i>	1.00±0.06 ^b	0.81	Negative Allometric	$W = 10.815(TL)^{0.81}$
<i>C. nigrodigitatus</i>	1.09±0.06 ^b	0.50	Negative Allometric	$W = 12.048(TL)^{0.50}$
<i>P. mariae</i>	2.13±0.18 ^a	0.08	Negative Allometric	$W = 9.114(TL)^{0.08}$
<i>S. melanotheron</i>	2.46±0.06 ^a	0.09	Negative Allometric	$W = 7.563(TL)^{0.09}$

^{abc} Means (±Standard error of mean) in the same column having similar superscript are not significantly different at $p < 0.05$; W = Weight; TL = Total Length

4.0 Discussion

Length-Weight relationship are significant as an important tool for the assessment of the growth pattern of fish species and the condition in which the growth. [10]. The simple linear regression slope (b) of the species. Length-Weight recorded during the period of the study fell within 0.048 and 0.068, this means that the fish experienced a negative allometric growth rate. This is in line with the growth coefficient (b) obtained of the two fish species ranged from 0.1441 to 0.8058 for *Oreochromis niloticus*, and from 0.1173 to 0.5457 for *Clarias gariepinus* reported by [11] in Wudil River. This is in disagreement with the study by [12], who recorded the values of regression coefficient ' b ' for length-weight relationships of 0.8313, 0.9517, 0.9629, 0.9223, and 0.8726 in *C. gariepinus* fed with various concentration of *Anisophyl lealaurina* seed meal. Factors such as stress resulting from overcrowding, overfishing, water quality parameters, pathogen and diseases, and inadequate nutrition could impact fish allometry.

The Length of (*Chrysichthys filamentous* 27.10 ± 1.50cm), (*Chrysichthys nigrodigitatus* 25.50 ± 0.50cm), (*Pelmatolapia mariae* 16.73 ± 0.66cm), (*Sarotherodon melanotheron* 15.35 ± 0.35cm) is significantly higher compared to (*Sarotherodon melanotheron* 13.80 ± 3.70cm), (*T. mariae* 10.10 ±

3.63cm), (*O. niloticus* 10.8 ± 3.42cm), (*C. guntheri* 10.38 ± 1.33cm) from a study by [13].

The weight of (*C. filamentous* 198.50 ± 20.50g), (*C. nigrodigitatus* 180.00 ± 1.00g), (*P. mariae* 98.67 ± 5.36g), (*S. melanotheron* 89.00 ± 4.00g) compared to (*S. melanotheron* 123.30 ± 11.10g), (*T. mariae* 27.90 ± 49.86g), (*O. niloticus* 53.63 ± 65.94g) [13] is high except *S. melanotheron* which is higher when compared to *P. elmatolapia* and *S. melanotheron* from present study. As observed in this study the condition factor was relatively high (*Chrysichthys filamentous* 1.00 ± 0.06), (*C. nigrodigitatus* 1.09 ± 0.06), (*P. mariae* 2.13 ± 0.18), (*S. melanotheron* 2.46 ± 0.06) compared to (*C. nigrodigitatus* 0.970 ± 0.06), (*S. galilaeus* 0.978 ± 0.05), (*H. odoe* 1.081 ± 0.006) from a study by [14]. This contrast might be due to season, species, nature of the water body during the period of study. [5] reported season and reproductive status to have regulatory effects on CF. Kuriakose, 2014 stated different fish species are influenced by many factors, including the quantity of food available and the quality of water, as well as the size, age, and sexual maturity of a fish

The condition factor gives information on the physiological condition of fish in relation to its welfare. Fish wellbeing varies between species and space [15]. [16] reported that fishes with a low condition index are presumably believed to have

experienced adverse, physical, environment or insufficient nutrition. The k value of the experiment ranges from 1.00 to 2.46. This is also not in agreement with the work done by [17], who recorded the k value of their experiment to be between 0.8313 and 0.9629. However, the result is not too far from condition factor (k) of 1.21 for *H. bidorsalis*; 1.57 for *H. niloticus*; 2.40 for *C. citharus* and 1.60 for *S. nigrita*. reported by [18] in Ona River. K value of fish less than 1.0 shows that the fish is not in good condition (poor, long and thin), while K-value above 1 represent a better conditioned fish [19]

5.0 Conclusion

The study of length weight relationship and condition factor can be affected by adverse environmental conditions and poor physiological condition leading to very low reproduction rate of the fishes and ultimately halt fishing activities of the area. This study on Length-Weight Relationship and condition factor has provided information on the well-being of some commercially exploited fish species in the study areas. All the fish species exhibited negative allometric growth pattern which shows that the fish lengths are not growing in similar rate to weight increase.

6.0 Acknowledgement

The authors graciously acknowledge the efforts of the fishermen, villagers, transporters, laboratory technologists and researchers who contributed their efforts and intellect to the success of this study.

7.0 Conflict of interest

The authors hereby affirm that there is no conflict of interest in the research as at the time of manuscript submission and are open to discussion if any arises.

8.0 References

- [1] Helfman GC, Farcey BJ. The Diversity of Fishes, Blackell Publishing Company, 1997.
- [2] Viadero RJ. Water Quality Factors Affecting Fish Growth and Production, <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119300762.wts011>: Wiley Online Library, 2019.
- [3] Ward FE. How to study the impact of environmental factors on fish., [Cited 26 Dec. 2023}. [Internet]. Available: <https://meekbond.com/study-impact-environmental-factors-fish-health/>.
- [4] Fishbase, Online Fish Identification Sheet, fishbase: <http://www.fishbase.org/search.php>., 2013.
- [5] Dinh QM, Dittman S, Tran DD. Morphometric Variation of Parapocryptes serperaster (Gobiidae) in Dry and wet seasons in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam: Ichthyological Research. 2016;63, pp. 267-274.
- [6] Bagenal TB, Tesch FW. Age and Growth. Oxford: Blackwell Scientific Publication, Methods for Assessment of Fish Production in Freshwaters; 1978; 101-136.
- [7] Froese R. Cube law, condition factor and weight-length relationships: history, meta-analysis and recommendations; Journal of Applied Ichthyology. 2006; 22: 241-253.
- [8] Idodo-Umeh GO. Freshwater fishes of Nigeria: Taxonomy, Ecological note, Diet and utilization; Edo State, Nigeria: Idodo-Umeh Publishers, 2003.
- [9] Bagenal TB, Tech FW. Age and growth," in *Methods for Assessment of Fish Production in Fresh Waters.*, Oxford, Blackwell Scientific Publications; 101-136.1978.
- [10] Kolher, N. Casey,J. and Turner, P. Length-weight relationships for 13species of sharks from the western North Atlantic. Fish. Bull. 1995; 93 (8): 412-418.
- [11] Getso BU, Abdullahi JM, YolaI A. Length-weight relationship and condition factor of *Clarias gariepinus* and *Oreochromis niloticus* of Wudil River, Kano, Nigeria. Agro-Science. 2017; 16(1) 1-4.
- [12] Olapade, OJ, Conteh KU. Growth performance, length-weight relationship and condition factor of *Clarias gariepinus* fed *Anisophyllea laurina* seed meal substitute. Journal of Applied Sciences and Environmental Management. 2019; 23: 505.
- [13] Atama CI, Okeke OC, Ekeh FN, Ezenwaji NE, OnahI E, Ivoke N, Onaja US, Eyo JE. Length-Weight Relationship and Condition Factor of Six Cichlid (Cichlidae: Perciformis) Species of Anambra River, Nigeria., Journal of Fisheries and Aquaculture. 2013; 4(2): 82-86.

- [14] Abdul WO, Omoniyi IT, Adekoya EO, Adeosun FI, Odulate OO, Idowu AA, Olajide AE, Olowe OS. Length-weight relationship and condition factor of some commercial fish species in Ogun State coastal estuary, Nigeria., *Ife Journal of Agriculture*.2016; 28(1).
- [15] Abdoli A, Allahyari S, Kiabi BH, Patimar R, Ghelichi A, Mostafavi H., Aghili SM, Rasooli P. Length-weight relationships for seven Gobiid fish species in the Southeastern Caspian Sea basin, Iran. *Journal of Applied Ichthyology*. 2009; 25: 785-786.
- [16] Shakir HA, Qazi JI, Hussain H, Alli S. “Growth coefficient and condition factor of three carp species reared under semi-intensive culture. *Punjab Univ. J. Zool*. 2010. 25; 1-2: 13-20.
- [17] Zamani-Faradonbe M, Eagderi S, Shahbazi NS. “Length-weight relationships and condition factor of three fish species from Taleghan River (Alborz Province, Iran).*Journal of Advanced Botany and Zoology*. 2015; 2: 1-39.
- [18] Ekelemu KJ, Samuel AAZ. “Growth patterns and condition factors of four dominant fish species in lake Ona, Southern Nigeria.” *Journal of Agriculture and Veterinary Sciences*. 2012;4.
- [19] Barnham C, Baxter A. Condition Factor, K, for Salmonid Fish, *Fisheries Note*;1998pp. 1-3.
- [20] Anene A. Condition Factor of Four Cichlid Species of a Man-made Lake in Imo State, South-eastern Nigeria. *Turk. J. Fish. Aquat Sci*. 2005; 5: 43-47.

